

Uncanny Semantics: How AI and Human Authors Use Language Differently in Academic Writing

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Abstract

This study explores the semantic differences between human-written and AI-generated academic texts by applying distributional semantics and word embedding techniques to a curated corpus of 325 introductions from linguistic articles. The corpus includes human-authored texts as well as AI-generated texts produced by six prominent language models (models from OpenAI, Google, and DeepSeek, each in a base and advanced version advertised for advanced reasoning). Each topic was prompted in two different ways: plain and academic. Using cosine similarity-based clustering, the most frequently occurring lemmas were grouped into semantic categories. The analysis reveals an overuse of positive-evaluative and structurally analytical vocabulary (e.g., *analysis, methodology, central*) in AI-generated texts, particularly those prompted in an academic tone. In contrast, human-authored texts tend to employ more epistemically cautious and critical language (e.g., *possibly, inconsistent, by no means*). These findings suggest that while large language models, when prompted accordingly, are focused on mimicking the surface form of academic writing, they tend to avoid critical engagement with approaches or data (and sometimes counterfactually overstate their importance). Moreover, they use epistemically relevant markers (expressing either certainty or uncertainty and connecting propositions coherently) far less frequently than human authors. I propose that this lack of epistemic markers (as well as the confidence with which the AIs exaggerate the importance of some approaches or data) can be explained by the AI's lack of a proposition-based epistemic system. Unlike humans, who react to epistemic uncertainty with dissonance and uncanniness, AIs are known to deal with epistemic uncertainty with overconfidence and inaccurate predictions. In this sense, the findings are in line with recent AI research. The results have implications for linguistic AI detection, authorship authenticity, and the evolving role of stylistic evaluation in academic discourse.

1 Introduction: The Uncanny Valley of AI

With large language models (LLMs) on the rise, distinguishing between human-authored and AI-generated academic texts has become increasingly challenging (Frank et al. 2023). This issue is particularly pressing in academic contexts, where authorship relates not only to intellectual property but also to the evaluation of professional competence (e.g., in student assignments or peer-reviewed research).

While the phenomenon of the *Uncanny Valley* — a drop in likability when artificial agents appear almost, but not fully, human — was originally described in robotics (Mori 1970/2012), it may also apply to textual artifacts that attempt to reproduce the style of human writing in a specific domain. Readers frequently report an intuitive sense that AI-generated texts feel ‘off’, even when they closely mimic human style and are difficult to distinguish from human-authored texts by objective criteria. Following Mori’s concept, I refer to this phenomenon as the *Uncanny Valley Effect* (hereafter UVE) of AI-generated texts. It has been theorized that the UVE originates from a general cognitive dissonance caused by categorical uncertainty (Categorical Uncertainty Hypothesis; cf. e.g., MacDorman and Chattopadhyay 2016; Wiese and Weis 2020). In the case of texts, this uncertainty may arise from doubts about the authenticity of the expressed ideas, the genre, the overall communicative intent, etc. This uncertainty seems to stem primarily from semantic content rather than purely formal or stylistic features. For example, Gao et al. (2023) show that human reviewers tasked with identifying AI-generated texts in mixed corpora likely do not rely on the same features as automated detection tools, suggesting a fundamentally different evaluation process. These reviewers often cited implausible or hallucinated information, as well as a general sense of vagueness or superficiality, as indicators of AI authorship.

Existing AI-detection tools currently rely primarily on stylometric or statistical features (e.g., perplexity values, sentence length, or token frequencies; cf. Desaire et al. 2023; Ofgang 2023). Yet such approaches do not address the semantic and evaluative dimensions that likely contribute to readers’ intuitive sense of weirdness.

This paper aims to explore these semantic dimensions by clustering frequent lemmas in a mixed (human- and AI-authored) corpus of 325 German academic text introductions, using a cosine similarity threshold of 0.7. Six prominent language models (models from OpenAI, Google, and DeepSeek, each in a base and advanced version advertised for ‘advanced reasoning’) were used. All topics originated from the field of German syntax. Each topic was prompted in two different ways: plain and academic. The results show that AI-generated texts tend to employ analytical and methodological terminology more frequently than human authors, while avoiding propositionally connective and evaluative terms. Therefore, the AI texts may appear academic on the surface but lack argumentative depth as well as critical and constructive engagement, e.g., formulating hypotheses. In addition, AI models were shown to overstate the importance of topics and theories in their field by applying positively evaluative vocabulary

(see *zentral*-category). I argue that these findings may be related to the way AIs deal with the problem of epistemic uncertainty.

2 Method

2.1 Corpus

For this study, the introduction sections of 25 peer-reviewed articles from the field of German-language linguistics were extracted. To rule out the possibility of AI-generated content in the ‘human’ texts, only articles from the ‘pre-AI’ era were selected, effectively covering a publication range from 1978 to 2021. All articles were, in one way or another, related to syntactic research on the left periphery of the sentence, addressing topics like verb fronting, prefield occupation, multiple prefield occupation (most commonly V3), pre-prefield occupation, left peripheral adverbial positioning, and non-standard constructions in spoken language associated with these phenomena. This ensured a degree of topical diversity within the corpus while maintaining a coherent overarching research domain and avoiding the level of semantic entropy that we would expect when comparing, for instance, syntactic studies with those focused on sociolinguistics.

In order to further reduce semantic entropy, all linguistic examples or transcriptions of original spoken or written language provided by the authors (most commonly in the form of numbered examples such as (1)) were excluded from the corpus, as such examples may introduce arbitrary, topic-irrelevant content and artificially inflate lexical or structural variety.

(1) After three vodka shots, Mary finally had the courage to kiss Peter.

Next, a total of six AI models were tasked with generating texts. These included the recent standard models from OpenAI (ChatGPT-4o), Google (Gemini Flash 2.0), and DeepsSeek (V3), as well as their respective counterparts marketed for more ‘advanced reasoning’ capabilities: ChatGPT-4o1, Gemini Flash 2.0 Thinking, and DeepSeek V3-R1.

Provider	Base Model	Advanced Model
ChatGPT	ChatGPT-4o	ChatGPT-4o1
Gemini	Gemini Flash 2.0	Gemini Flash 2.0 Thinking
DeepsSeek	DeepsSeek V3	DeepsSeek V3-R1

Table 1: Overview of AI models used

For each human-authored reference text, each model was instructed to generate two introductions (TextA and TextB) to a scientific article on the same topic. To prevent the texts from influencing one another, each was generated in a separate instance (new chat) of the respective AI application, with no additional context or further information provided by the user. The two AI-generated texts per model were produced using different prompts: TextA was generated using a

straightforward, minimal prompt, while TextB was created using an extended prompt that requested a more academic writing style, the inclusion of references to scientific literature, and adherence to the Harvard citation style.

Prompt	German	English translation
TextA	<i>Schreibe eine Einleitung für einen sprachwissenschaftlichen Aufsatz über das Thema [Thema].</i>	<i>Write an introduction to a linguistic paper on the topic [topic].</i>
TextB	<i>Schreibe eine Einleitung für einen sprachwissenschaftlichen Aufsatz über das Thema [Thema]. Bediene dich eines akademischen Stils, benutze die Harvard-Zitierweise, verweise auf einschlägige Literatur. Beschreibe, wie für eine wissenschaftliche Einleitung typisch, worum es in dem Artikel geht und wie vorgegangen wird.</i>	<i>Write an introduction to a linguistic paper on the topic [topic]. Use an academic style, apply the Harvard citation style, and refer to relevant literature. As is typical for a scholarly introduction, describe the subject of the article and outline the methodological approach.</i>

Table 2: Prompts given to the language models

Only the main article texts were extracted from the output. Meta-comments from the AI and appended bibliographies were excluded, as such elements are not typically found in the introduction sections of scientific papers. Also, as with the human texts, numbered examples such as (1) have been excluded for the same reasons mentioned above. Combined with the human texts, a total of 325 texts were analyzed.

2.2 Data

For each prompt type and model, the output texts were merged into a single composite text. For example, all TextA outputs from ChatGPT-4o were combined into one text, while all TextB outputs from the same model formed another, and so on for each model. In the same manner, all human-authored texts were merged into a single composite text, as if they had been produced by one *model*. Some cases of cross-lingual contamination were encountered in the data: Five insertions of Russian words were detected, such as in (2):

- (2) [...] lassen sich diese *закономерности* erklären?
 [...] let pron-ref these ‘*patterns*’ (Russian) explain
 (Gemini Flash 2.0 Breindl2012 TextA text set in Wegerhoff 2025a)

This issue might have multiple causes (imprecise training methods, suboptimal training data, decoder error, etc.) and is hard to predict as the training methods

and underlying technology for most common models are still undisclosed to the public (cf. Jiang et al. 2024). However, these cases were only encountered in 2 texts (Breindl2012 and Fiehler2015) in Wegerhoff (2025a), and are only present in outputs generated by Gemini Models, so their impact on the overall corpus data can be considered minimal.

For tokenization, the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK; Bird et al. 2009) was used. Lemmatization, POS-tagging and word embeddings were performed using spaCy (Honnibal et al. 2020) with the language model *de_core_news_lg*. In a nutshell, *word embedding* can be considered a machine learning method that tries to encode the meaning of a word as a multi-dimensional vector¹, similar (but not completely identical) to a feature-based semantic analysis of the meaning of words (for an introduction to feature-based semantics, cf. e.g., Hurford and Heasley 1983, for an introduction to word2vec encoding, cf. e.g., Mikolov et al. 2013, Aggarwal 2023, 99ff.). These features are not purely semantic, but encode any feature the machine learning algorithm deems relevant for distinguishing between words and may also include syntactic or probabilistic features. Words with similar meanings have similar embedding-vectors and thus are closer to each other in the vector space. The semantic similarity of words can be quantified by calculating the cosine of the angle between their respective embedding vectors (cosine similarity; cf. Singhal 2001, 46ff.). A smaller angle between vectors corresponds to a higher cosine value, indicating greater similarity. This, in theory, allows us to form semantic categories of words that objectively share similar semantic features.

In Wegerhoff (2025a), I developed a set of scripts that:

- identify and count the most frequent lemmas across different models and parts of speech, while also extracting stylometric features;
- group lemmas into semantic categories based on vector similarity and determine the most prevalent categories for each model.

The threshold for semantic clustering was set to a cosine similarity of 0.7. This value was chosen to group semantically similar lemmas without being overly specific. It should be noted that my aim was not to achieve the most fine-grained and efficient clustering—otherwise, a transformer-based model such as BERT and a higher similarity threshold would have been used. Instead, the aim was to test whether general, broader semantic patterns are visible across texts, even when using a relatively coarse-grained clustering method and comparatively small text corpus. As discussed in Section 1, human reviewers of academic texts seem to be sensitive to such differences, but their perception of semantic similarity is likely based on similarly broad and intuitive notions rather than fine-grained and computationally precise semantic clustering. Each category was labeled using the first lemma of the group as it appeared in the corpus. For example, the frequency of the group *analytisch* (*‘analytic’*) does not represent how often the lemma *analytisch* appeared in the corpus, but rather how often words with

¹In the case of spaCy’s *de_core_news_lg* model, there are 300 dimensions.

a cosine similarity of ≥ 0.7 to *analytisch* appeared in the corpus. Extremely common words (so called *stop-words*) were removed from the analysis using SpaCy’s predefined German stop-word list. The analysis was conducted through multiple experimental runs:

- A combined run that categorizes adjectives, adverbs, nouns, and verbs simultaneously in an overarching analysis.
- Separate runs that categorize adjectives, adverbs, nouns, and verbs individually, to prevent different parts of speech from influencing each other’s categorizations.
- A comparative run that categorizes two groups of parts of speech: adjectives and adverbs versus nouns and verbs.

3 Results

The primary goal of this analysis is to determine whether certain categories are noticeably over- /underrepresented in one model or text type, compared to the human text set. While there are numerous observations worth discussing, I will focus on the ones I found the most striking. A complete visual representation of each run’s results (heatmaps and category members) can be found in (Wegerhoff 2025b). Note that *de_core_news_lg* is not a transformer-based model but instead uses static (context-insensitive) part-of-speech (POS) tagging, which means that some POS might be misclassified, depending on the context. This is especially relevant for adjectives and adverbs, which, in this paper, are treated as one combined POS-group as mentioned above.

3.1 Nouns

The data show that the group *analyse* (*‘analysis’*) is strikingly overrepresented in the more elaborate, academic-specific TextB prompt.² The overrepresentation persists across all models, but the effect is most striking in both Gemini models:

²The group consists of the following analysis-related lemmas: *analyse* (*‘analysis’*), *auswertung* (*‘evaluation’*), *datenanalyse* (*‘data analysis’*), *evaluation* (*‘evaluation’*), *methodik* (*‘methodology’*).

Figure 1: Heatmap of the group *analyse*, showing absolute frequencies

A very similar pattern can be observed in the related adjective *analytisch*, which encompasses 13 lemmas that generally denote a scientific and methodical approach to a subject.³

This effect is likely attributable to Prompt B, which explicitly calls for an academic tone and a methodological approach, resulting in a higher frequency of lemmas the model associates with academic or methodological language. However, both prompts (A and B) made the model aware that the text to generate is for academic purposes and thus needs methodological approaches, but the explicit call for academic tone in Prompt B seemed to have amplified the use of methodological lemmas in the model.

Another interesting finding is that some AI models tend to explicitly refer to the structural role of the generated section within the broader (hypothetical) text, suggesting a degree of implicit awareness of academic text organization. Lemma categories related to text structure, such as *kapitel* (*‘chapter’*)⁴ and *abschnitt* (*‘section’*)⁵, are comparatively frequent in human-authored texts, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Across the AI-generated texts, these structural lemmas appear unevenly: the

³The lemmas in the *analytisch* category are: *analytisch* (*‘analytical’*), *dialogisch* (*‘dialogical’*), *differenzierend* (*‘differentiating’*), *empirisch* (*‘empirical’*), *fachsprachlich* (*‘technical’*), *graphisch* (*‘graphical’*), *holistisch* (*‘holistic’*), *logisch* (*‘logical’*), *philosophisch* (*‘philosophical’*), *pragmatisch* (*‘pragmatic’*), *systematisch* (*‘systematic’*), *systemisch* (*‘systemic’*), *topologisch* (*‘topological’*), *wissenschaftlich* (*‘scientific’*).

⁴The *kapitel* group consists solely of the lemma *kapitel*.

⁵The *abschnitt* group consists solely of the lemma *abschnitt*.

Figure 2: Heatmaps of the categories *kapitel* and *abschnitt*, showing absolute frequencies

group *kapitel* occurs in 6 out of 12 AI text sets, while *abschnitt* occurs in 5 out of 12. Their presence is strongly tied to the academic prompt (TextB), as shown by the higher averages in Table 3, whereas TextA rarely triggers such references. Importantly, the elevated averages for AI models are not uniform but are driven by a few outlier systems—most notably Gemini 2.0 thinking and ChatGPT-1 under the academic prompt—which show structural marker frequencies up to three times higher than the human baseline. Other models, by contrast, remain close to or even below human frequencies.

	Kapitel (\emptyset)	Abschnitt (\emptyset)
Advanced models	10,83	16,50
Normal models	8,00	2,17
TextA (Prompt A)	0,33	0,83
TextB (Prompt B)	18,50	17,83

Table 3: Average frequency of *kapitel* and *abschnitt* across all models by model type (normal vs. advanced reasoning) and prompt type (A vs. B)

This pattern suggests that meta-textual markers are more sensitive to prompt design than model sophistication. The extreme frequencies observed in some models likely reflect a form of surface-level mimicry: the models reproduce structural cues of academic writing (e.g., explicit chapter or section references) without necessarily engaging in deeper argumentative functions like hypothesis formulation. This observation is supported by the frequency of the *hypothese* (*‘hypothesis’*⁶ category, which is overrepresented in human texts compared to

⁶The group only consists of one lemma.

the AI’s texts and—again—completely missing in almost half the AI-generated text sets:

Figure 3: Heatmap of the group *Hypothese*, showing absolute frequencies.

3.2 Adjectives and Adverbs

With regard to adjectives and adverbs, the observation persists that the TextB text set seems to use structuring vocabulary significantly more frequently than the TextA text set and the human text set. This is, for example, visible in the *abschließend*-category, which consists of only two lemmas: *abschließend* (‘conclusively’) and *anschließend* (‘subsequently’):

As Figure 4 shows, the *abschließend* category, which denotes some kind of textual subsequence or conclusion, is overrepresented in the TextB set when compared to both the TextA and the human text set. There are also notable differences between human- and AI-generated texts regarding adjectives that evaluate the importance of a topic within the respective academic field. Compared to the average frequency of the *zentral* (‘central’, ‘crucial’)⁷ category in AI-generated texts (TextA and TextB), its frequency in the human-authored text is less than half as high, which means *zentral* is more than twice as likely to occur in AI-generated texts:

The AI tends to emphasize the importance of a topic for the respective scientific discipline, but sometimes overestimates its actual relevance in the academic

⁷the group consists of only one lemma (*zentral*).

Figure 4: Heatmap of the group *abschließend*, showing absolute frequencies

Text Type	frequency	
TextA	0,894	avg. per text Across all models
TextB	0,994	avg. per text Across all models
HumanText (Original)	0,4	average per text

Table 4: Average frequency per text of *zentral*-category

field. An example of this behavior is presented in (3), which originates from the ChatGPT4o generated introduction to the topic of the FreyPittner1998-text set (positioning of adverbials) Wegerhoff (2025a):

- (3) Die Frage nach der Positionierung von Adverbialen im deutschen Mittelfeld gehört zu den zentralen Themen der deutschen Syntaxforschung. (*The positioning of adverbials in the German middle field ranks among the central topics in the study of German syntax.*)

While it is undeniably true that (base-generated) adverbials are an important and much-discussed topic within German syntax research, describing them as a central focal point would be misleading. They represent just one of several phenomena explored within the field.

Human-authored texts, on the other hand, stand out through their use of connective, critical and epistemically evaluative expressions. A notable example is the *allenfalls* (*‘at most’*) group, which is remarkably large and comprises 32 lem-

mas.⁸ These lemmas are predominantly adverbs that serve to coherently connect propositions or express the speaker’s epistemic stance toward the proposition of the sentence, reaching from very careful assumptions (e.g., *womöglich* - ‘possibly’) to strong epistemic markers (e.g., *keinesfalls* - ‘by no means’). Depending on the prompt, the group is 8 to 11 times more likely to appear in the human texts compared to the AI-generated texts:

Text Type	Frequency	
TextA	0,407	avg. per text Across AI models
TextB	0,300	avg. per text Across AI models
HumanText (Original)	3,320	avg. per text

Table 5: Average frequencies per text of *allenfalls*-category:

Furthermore, the *uneinheitlich* (‘inconsistent’)⁹ category was found to be 6 to 8 times more frequently used in the human text set, indicating that human authors are more open to taking a critical stance towards existing theoretical models or datasets.

Text Type	Frequency	
TextA	0,407	avg. per text Across AI models
TextB	0,300	avg. per text Across AI models
HumanText (Original)	2,320	avg. per text

Table 6: Average frequencies per text of *uneinheitlich*-category

3.3 Verbs

The category *stehen*, consisting of the lemmas *stehen* and *stellen* (‘to stand’ and ‘to put’) is the most frequently used category among the verbs, both in the AI-generated texts and in the human texts, but is still about 2.5 times more likely to appear in human texts:

The reason for this high frequency likely is connected to the relatively general semantics of *stehen* and *stellen* and their frequent use in German idiomatic constructions, as in, e.g., *im Widerspruch stehen* (‘to be in contradiction with’).

⁸The group consists of *allenfalls* (‘at most’), *andererseits* (‘on the other hand’), *ansonsten* (‘otherwise’), *augenscheinlich* (‘apparently’), *demnach* (‘accordingly’), *dennoch* (‘nevertheless’), *ebenfalls* (‘also’), *fraglich* (‘questionable’), *freilich* (‘admittedly’), *gleichwohl* (‘nonetheless’), *gänzlich* (‘entirely’), *hingegen* (‘by contrast’), *insofern* (‘insofar’), *jedenfalls* (‘in any case’), *keinesfalls* (‘by no means’), *keineswegs* (‘in no way’), *lediglich* (‘merely’), *letztlich* (‘ultimately’), *möglicherweise* (‘possibly’), *namentlich* (‘namely’), *nämlich* (‘namely’), *offensichtlich* (‘obviously’), *tatsächlich* (‘in fact’), *teilweise* (‘partially’), *vermeintlich* (‘supposedly’), *vermutlich* (‘presumably’), *vielmehr* (‘rather’), *vordringlich* (‘pressingly’), *wiederum* (‘again’), *womöglich* (‘possibly’), *zumindest* (‘at least’), *üblicherweise* (‘typically’).

⁹the group consists of *uneinheitlich* (‘inconsistent’), *unterschiedlich* (‘different’), *weitgehend* (‘to a large extent’), *weitreichend* (‘far-reaching’)

Text Type	Frequency	
TextA	0,894	avg. per text Across AI models
TextB	0,947	avg. per text Across AI models
HumanText (Original)	2,24	avg. per text

Table 7: Average frequencies per text of *stehen*-category

Similar to the observations regarding the use of nouns, the use of explicitly analytical language is more prevalent in the AI texts. The category *analysiert* (consisting of *analysieren* - ‘to analyze’ and *untersuchen* - ‘to investigate’) is about 10-15 times more frequent in AI texts:

Text Type	Frequency	Note
TextA	0,407	avg. per text Across AI models
TextB	0,600	avg. per text Across AI models
HumanText (Original)	0,04	avg. per text

Table 8: Average frequencies per text of *analysiert*-category

As with the respective nouns (see above), the effect is stronger in the TextB text set where the AI was explicitly tasked with a more academic use of language.

4 Discussion

The results so far can be summarized as follows:

The human-written and AI-generated academic texts examined in this paper appear to differ in their use of evaluative language, particularly critical language. AI tends to exaggerate the importance and quality of topics and theories within their respective academic fields, sometimes in an imprecise or counterfactual way. Also, the AIs, at least in the TextB text set, overuse analytical and methodological terminology compared to humans. How can we explain this behavior?

The lack of epistemically evaluative terms observable in the AI-generated data can be explained in terms of how the AI ‘thinks’. As sentences are generated probabilistically, the AI does not represent knowledge as an interconnected system of propositions in the way humans are believed to do—that is, not as a coherent belief system comprising true propositions, as theorized in the tradition of propositional semantics, e.g., Frege’s (1892) notion of propositions of thoughts, Tarski’s (1944) semantic theory of truth and Hintikka’s (1962) epistemic logic. Transformer-based AIs, instead, approximate patterns that correlate with truth through statistical relationships encoded in their learned internal weights, rather than representing truth as an explicit propositional system. This probabilistic approximation of truth can be overridden or constrained by (typically undisclosed) system-level prompts provided by the AI developers (e.g., instructions such as “Do not engage in conversations about the political status of Taiwan”,

“Do not provide information on xyz”, “Assume that xyz is always true” etc.). These system-level prompts contain so called *guardrails*, which are mostly intended to offer users a safe, positive, and optimistic experience while avoiding conflict, controversy, dangerous information or public backlash (for guardrails, cf. e.g., Dong et al. 2024; Ayyamperumal and Ge 2024). These guardrails may account for the AI’s avoidance of negative criticism that can be observed in the data. Thus, the texts appear rather uncritical and reassuring, which is shown in the data’s lack of critical expressions in AI texts when compared to human texts.

But beyond these external guardrails, an AI—at least at this point—has no internal representation of a consistent belief or knowledge system that it adheres to, and, as a consequence, it also lacks an accurate representation of what it does *not* know. Therefore, when confronted with epistemic or aleatoric uncertainties (e.g., out-of-distribution data, contradictions, or niche topics such as, for example, base-generated adverbials in the topological middle field), an AI tends to produce inaccurate predictions, and often does so with unwarranted confidence. This, in fact, is a very well known phenomenon in the field of AI research (cf. e.g., Manchinal et al. 2025; Papernot et al. 2015; Hüllermeier and Waegeman 2021; Goodfellow et al. 2015; Hendrycks and Gimpel 2018). The type of uncertainty most problematic in our case is epistemic, as it stems from gaps in the training data. Since AIs lack an explicit sense of their own uncertainty, they have little need for linguistic markers to express epistemic (un)certainly, which results in a markedly lower frequency of such terms in their output. This tendency toward overconfidence may also account for the overestimation of a topic’s importance within an academic field, as noted above. In this sense, the findings here are in line with research on behavior of AIs that are confronted with classification uncertainty.

Regarding the importance of the prompt, the abundant use of analytical terms such as *analyse* (‘*analysis*’) seems to be much more prominent in the TextB text set than in every other text set. The same is true for the *abschließend* (‘*concluding*’)-group containing text-structuring adverbs and adjectives. This illustrates that a more elaborate prompt generally has a much larger effect on the result than the choice of a more advanced alternative model or different AI. The AI models discussed in this paper, in average, use these terms excessively more often than human authors, likely in an attempt to give the TextB text set a more academic flavor compared to the more general prompt in TextA (see also the *abschnitt-* and *kapitel-*group in section 3.1, where TextB contains more text-structuring vocabulary than TextA). Nevertheless, when it comes to the usage of vocabulary that is associated with substantial theoretical reasoning, including the formulation of hypotheses and the application of nuanced, domain-specific terminology, AI models remain inferior to human authors, as seen above.

In this regard, the data supports the observations made by the blinded reviewers in Gao et al. (2023) regarding the vagueness present in the AI-generated texts. Following the data discussed here, this vagueness can be characterized as both an intuitively and empirically striking contrast: On the one hand, there

is an over-representation of academic and analytical vocabulary employed by the AI models (particularly in the TextB text set). On the other hand, there is a noticeable avoidance of adverbs and connectors that connect and (critically) evaluate propositions within a broader academic idea or framework (as seen above). While the AI models, on average, exaggerate their methodical and analytical approach by linguistic means, at the same time they seem to avoid it in practice. Readers who are regularly exposed to academic writing may find this strategy irritating, thereby experiencing what was described as the UVE in section 1. While the frequent use of methodological terminology suggests a highly academic and methodologically rigorous paper, the text ultimately fails to meet these expectations on an argumentative level—resulting in categorical uncertainty (regarding text type or the author’s academic background, for example).

Ironically, both the AI and the readers are confronted with categorical uncertainty, albeit in different ways. The general-purpose AI faces epistemic uncertainty when required to generate predictions in highly academic and niche contexts for which it was not explicitly trained. As discussed above, AIs typically respond to such uncertainty with surprisingly high confidence. Because of their missing epistemic system, in a Socratic sense, AIs ‘don’t know that they don’t know’, as Manchingal et al. (2025) point out. Human readers, by contrast, encounter categorical uncertainty: the text they are reading appears academic on the surface, yet deviates epistemically and formally from what they would normally expect of academic writing. This mismatch renders the text subtly unsettling, uncanny, or weird. For future research, it would be worthwhile to investigate whether this effect also occurs in readers with less experience in engaging with academic texts.

As for the data, the results must be taken *cum grano salis*: with only 25 human-written texts, the reference set is comparatively small and limited to a narrow range of interconnected topics. The method and dataset described in this paper was rather explorative. The findings may not be fully generalizable to larger datasets or texts from other academic domains, although similar results can be expected when using similar prompt styles. As AI is developing fast, the results of this paper may not be reproducible with newer models in the future. It should be noted that the models used in this study were not specifically designed for academic writing—nor are they marketed as such—but rather represent the most widely accessible and commonly used general-purpose AIs available at the time of analysis. The effects discovered in this paper may be considerably less striking with AI models specialized for more academic tasks (such as, e.g., Claude 3 Opus). Conversely, I would also expect the differences between human-authored and AI-generated texts to diminish if the human corpus consisted of student assignments rather than peer-reviewed publications, as the former are typically more descriptive and less critically engaged with academic discourse.

From a methodological perspective, spaCy is an out-of-the-box NLP toolkit and is therefore relatively static in its application. It is not ideally suited for highly

specialized academic NLP tasks. Notably, the word embeddings provided by the *de_core_news_lg* model were static, meaning they did not account for contextual variation in meaning. Unlike transformer-based language models (such as BERT), these embeddings assign each word a single, context-independent vector representation. In addition, a different cosine similarity threshold would have yielded different clustering results, but the spaCy toolkit and the chosen threshold of 0.7 appeared widely appropriate for identifying semantically aligned lemmas (i.e., those that, quite literally in vector space, point roughly in the same direction) and grouping them into meaningful categories.

The findings in this paper may have practical implications for future AI-detection tools. Rather than relying solely on perplexity scores, stylometric profiles, or other purely stochastic indicators, effective detectors should integrate semantic-category analysis. Combining statistical features with meaning-based cues will provide a more nuanced understanding of the textual signals—both intuitive and quantitative—that distinguish human from AI-generated writing.

5 Conclusion

This exploratory study examined semantic differences between human-written and AI-generated academic texts using a clustering approach based on cosine similarity (threshold 0.7). The findings indicate that AI-generated texts more frequently employ analytical and methodological terminology than human authors, yet tend to avoid connective terms that link and evaluate propositions. This results in texts that appear formally academic but lack argumentative depth as well as critical and constructive engagement, e.g., formulating hypotheses. In addition, AI models were shown to overstate the importance of topics and theories in their field by applying positively evaluative vocabulary (see *zentral*-category).

I suggest that these findings can be explained by differences in how humans and transformer-based AIs represent and generate knowledge and beliefs. Unlike humans, who are believed to organize beliefs and knowledge as an epistemic system based on propositions, AIs approximate patterns statistically and operate without a proposition-based, internal epistemic system. As a consequence, AIs rarely use epistemic markers or connectors (as seen with the *allenfalls*-group) as they have no graded sense of epistemic (un)certainty. The absence of an AI's model of its own (un)certainty contributes to a tendency toward imprecise but overconfident predictions, which is a very well-known issue and in line with research in the field of machine learning. The avoidance of critically evaluative markers may further be reinforced by system-level guardrails designed to prevent conflict or controversy.

Methodologically, the study demonstrates that prompt design exerts a strong influence on linguistic output, arguably more so than the choice of model itself. While more elaborate prompts encourage greater use of analytical and text-structuring vocabulary, they do not bridge the gap between AI- and human-authored texts in terms of critical and domain-specific reasoning. These find-

ings align with earlier observations of vagueness and overgeneralization in AI-generated writing and may contribute to a subtle sense of uncanniness in readers — a phenomenon that I compared to the Uncanny Valley Effect (UVE).

The study’s limitations include the small size and narrow topical scope of the human reference corpus as well as the use of static word embeddings for semantic clustering. Future work should replicate this analysis with larger and more diverse datasets, incorporate contextual embeddings, and investigate how specialized academic LLMs compare to general-purpose models. Moreover, reader-response studies could test whether the UVE observed here—caused by the mismatch between academic form and lack of epistemic substance—also occurs among less experienced readers.

Finally, the results have practical implications for AI-detection and quality assessment: instead of relying exclusively on stochastic indicators such as perplexity, effective detection should integrate semantic and evaluative dimensions. Combining statistical features with meaning-based cues may enable more effective tools to differentiate between human and AI-generated academic writing.

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